

ISic2707

I.Sicily inscription 2707

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea"

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334792

1. Κλαῦ-

2. δις Σύ-

3. ντρο-

4. φος.

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645127

PHI 334792

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 686

Calderone, S. 1949. Analecta epigraphica liparensia. *Epigraphica*. 11: 49-60. At 54 no.3

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